

How Perceived Content Quality Drives User Recommendations in OTT Services?

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Abstract : Purpose - Traditional content providers have been overtaken by over-the-top (OTT) services, which offer streaming video across all devices in an internet environment. However, it is unclear from the available data how user suggestions in OTT Services are influenced by the perceived quality of the material.

Objective - This study aims to investigate how perceived content quality drives user recommendations in OTT Services.

Methodology - The study uses a primary data collection methodology in which respondents who are frequent users of over-the-top (OTT) services are surveyed. This study examined the relationships between various dimensions, including Recommendation Behaviour (RB), Continuous Intention to Use (CIU), Perceived Content Quality (PCQ), and Perceived Enjoyment (PE), using statistical analysis.

Findings - This study found that Perceived Content Quality, Perceived Enjoyment, and Continuous Intention to Use are positively associated with the Recommendation Behaviour of OTT Users.

Research Practical and Social Implications - The results further clarify that one of the most effective features of over-the-top (OTT) video streaming technology in gauging a user's persistent intention is content. It gives OTT content makers insightful feedback to help them concentrate more on the requirements and expectations of the user base.

Originality/Value - The study's findings offer a novel perspective for service providers to enhance the Content Quality and Recommendation Behaviour of OTT users.

Keywords - Perceived Content Quality, Perceived Enjoyment, Continuous Intention to Use, Recommendation Behaviour, OTT Services.

Paper Type – Research Paper

Introduction

Over-the-Top (OTT) services have emerged as a major player in the quickly changing digital entertainment market, providing consumers with never-before-seen levels of access to a vast variety of content. Understanding the elements that influence user engagement and loyalty has become crucial for service providers as the competition among OTT platforms heats up. Among these variables, user behaviour is largely determined by perceived content quality, especially when it comes to content suggestions.

OTT platforms are largely shaped by user-generated recommendations, which are frequently shared via social media, online reviews, and personal networks. In addition to influencing prospective users' decision-making, these suggestions raise the platform's profile and legitimacy in a congested industry. It is still unclear how much users' perceptions of the quality of the material influence their recommendations for over-the-top services.

User recommendations in over-the-top (OTT) services are heavily influenced by the quality of the content, which in turn shapes how users see and suggest these platforms to others. Positive user experiences are the result of high-quality content, and these experiences are critical for encouraging word-of-mouth marketing and producing natural recommendations. OTT platforms have the potential to increase user engagement by providing superior content. Strong narratives, excellent production qualities, and original content keep audiences interested and boost usage and retention. Because they are confident in the value the platform offers, satisfied users are more likely to suggest it to friends and family. Strong emotional reactions are frequently elicited by high-quality content, leaving viewers with unforgettable memories. Content that touches people emotionally, whether it's a thought-provoking documentary, a gripping television series, or a moving film, inspires people to share their experiences. Sincere excitement and a genuine connection are the foundation of what makes personal suggestions so effective.

Viewers regularly offer their opinions on social media and review platforms in the digital era. Positive reviews and social media buzz are generated by high-quality content, which increases the platform's appeal and visibility. Positive social media shares and online reviews serve as endorsements, swaying prospective subscribers who value the opinions of their peers more than conventional advertising. The practice of binge-watching, in which viewers watch several episodes or seasons at once, has become more common thanks to OTT services. Users are more inclined to talk about well-produced shows in their social groups after binge watching them. As a result of their continued involvement, viewers naturally spread the news about the programme and the platform to others. Viewers experience a sense of urgency and FOMO (fear of missing out) when exposed to high-quality, exclusive information. Users are more inclined to suggest a platform to their peers in order to ensure that they are also aware of its offerings, which increases the platform's appeal and subscriber base, when it delivers must-watch series or films that are unavailable elsewhere.

In order to close this disparity, this study looks at how consumers' opinions of the quality of the material affect their propensity to suggest OTT services. This study looks at how user contentment, recommendation behaviour, and content quality interact in order to try to offer light on how OTT service providers should make strategic decisions. It is imperative to comprehend these dynamics in order to develop content strategies that will ultimately support the growth and longevity of the platform by satisfying users and promoting organically through user referrals.

Literature Review

Perceived Content Quality

"Perceived content quality" is how users or consumers evaluate the calibre of the material they come across, usually in circumstances pertaining to digital or media. It is a subjective assessment that is dependent on how each person views and judges the qualities, overall value, relevancy, and believability of the content Madi, J. et. al (2024). Quality of material is generally assessed by users based on how well it suits their requirements or interests. Users tend to view information as higher quality if it is highly related to their search query or interests. Users evaluate the correctness of the information provided and the reliability of the source. People tend to view content from reliable sources as being of a higher calibre. Writing that is clear, concise, and devoid of grammar mistakes is frequently seen as superior to other types of content Fan, L. et. al (2024). The perceived quality of multimedia content, such graphics or movies, can be greatly influenced by the production values and visual quality. In order to improve the perceived quality of their content, marketers and content creators frequently work to create content that is in line with the expectations and inclinations of their intended audience Yousaf, A. et al, (2021). OTT platforms have implemented a third technique that involves understanding user preferences and fostering engagement through content, recommendation engines, and binge-watching. By maximising the network effect of same-sided users, content diversification and platform extension tactics drive additional growth Kour, G & Chhabria, B, (2022). The widely dispersed populace watches nearly one-eighth of a day on their preferred drama, TV show, or film and has access to their favourite content on numerous screens. Different business models have been developed by regional, national, and international firms for content provision and income generation Saha, S & Al, E, (2021). To keep subscribers engaged as active users, marketers should take these developments into account and modify their content plans. Customers demand that marketers lower rates, reorganise subscription packages, expand the selection of content, and create new, innovative subscription plans that provide customers greater freedom and flexibility Sharma, K, & Lulandala, E. E, (2023).

H1: Perceived content quality positively influences users' recommendation behavior.

Perceived Enjoyment

The assessment of perceived enjoyment is individualised and subjective. It differs from person to person and is subject to personal choices, feelings, and expectations. It has a lot to do with how one feels and reacts emotionally to something. Positive feelings like happiness, contentment, or amusement are frequently associated with activities, goods, or content that are deemed entertaining (Winarno., et al 2021). Perceived enjoyment plays a major role in the success of novels, movies, video games, and other media in the context of entertainment. Audiences are more inclined to respond favourably to enjoyable entertainment experiences. In order to increase perceived enjoyment and consumer satisfaction, marketers frequently try to establish pleasant emotional associations with their goods or services (Yu *et al.*, 2024). When it comes to encouraging behaviour that involves utilising the OVO application to transact online, subjective standards are crucial. Compared to other external variables, such as self-

efficacy and felt satisfaction, this role is increasing in significance as indicated by the path coefficient and increased rated usefulness Winarno, W.A., et al, (2021). Perceived utility and perceived cognitive benefits, in particular, are the two main variables affecting perceived enjoyment. Based on the results, instructors should aim to promote cognitive engagement and take perceived value into account, as this will affect students' readiness to use online learning management systems for learning. If instructors fail to encourage students' perceived satisfaction, they will probably always be dealing with poor turnout and pupils who are not engaged. This is troublesome not just for instructors but also for governments and higher education headship who want to build a nation via high-quality instructing and learning (Van der Walt, F. et al., (2024).

H2: Perceived enjoyment has a positive effect on user's recommendation behavior.

Continuous Intention to Use

Stronger intentions to stick with a technology or system are typically linked to high user satisfaction ratings. Loyal customers are more likely to be satisfied users. Even though they are not really happy with a technology, people can keep using it out of habit or because they have grown accustomed to it. The intention to continue might also be influenced by habitual use Gupta, Wajid and Gaur, (2024). When deciding whether to stick with the current technology or system, users might weigh the expenses and work required in making the changeover. Exorbitant switching fees could discourage users from giving up. Businesses and developers can benefit greatly from user feedback regarding their intentions to continue in order to improve and maintain a user base. Comprehending the aim of continuance holds significance for companies looking to hold onto clients and promote prolonged usage of their goods or services Abbasi *et al.*, (2024). When predicting and analysing user behaviour about the continued use of technology or services, the concept of continuity intention to use is employed. Numerous things affect it, such as habit, switching costs, perceived utility, and user pleasure. Organisations may make more educated decisions about marketing, client retention, and product development by having a thorough understanding of these aspects Foroughi *et al.*, (2024). Consumers who utilise over-the-top (OTT) platforms have a favourable impact on perceived value and intention to continue using the platform to subscribe to content; nevertheless, convenience is a problem that has to be fixed. Enhancements are also required for the hazards associated with costs and technology. Examining the contents of the convenience questionnaire in particular, automatically chooses new and popular content to provide notification services or improve the selection, search, and recommendation of different content Gupta, S., & Tomar, R, (2023). User satisfaction was positively and strongly impacted by quality, service quality, and user motivation. The impression of the net advantages and the purpose to continue using a platform for streaming were positively and significantly impacted by user happiness. Perceived net benefits had a favourable and noteworthy relationship with the purpose to stick with a specific platform for streaming. Confirmed was the moderating role of emotional involvement in the relationship between perceived net benefits and user pleasure Kuo, C.-S. and Hsu, C.-C, (2022). There are multiple noteworthy correlations between perceived worth and continuing purpose. Specifically, Social presence exerts a strong influence

on perceived worth, felt density of traffic, vulnerability to the impact of information, and faith in media personalities. Furthermore, the relationship between perceived worth and purpose to continue is moderated by trust in broadcasters Chong, H. X. et al. (2023).

H3: Continuous intention to use positively influences users' recommendation behavior.

Recommendation Behaviour

Businesses and platforms that employ recommendation systems to increase user engagement, satisfaction, and conversion rates must comprehend suggestion behaviour. The process of coming up with ideas or recommendations is one example of recommendation behaviour. Depending on their requirements, interests, and preferences, users can choose to accept, reject, or ignore recommendations. Users' decision-making processes can be greatly impacted by recommendation behaviour Nandukrishna, (2024). Recommendations are frequently used by users to find new products, choose what to buy, choose what to consume, and interact with others on social media. A feedback loop is frequently present in recommendation behaviour, where user interactions and recommendations' replies are utilised to hone and enhance the recommendation algorithms Sahu *et al.*, (2024). A number of variables, including the recommendations' relevancy and precision as well as the recommendation process's transparency, might affect trust. Ethical concerns have been brought up by recommendation systems' actions and how they affect users' decisions, particularly when recommendations have the potential to change people's attitudes, beliefs, or actions. The ethical implications of recommendation systems encompass questions of privacy, manipulation, and bias Vyshakh *et al.*, (2023). Businesses must comprehend suggestion behaviour in order to optimise their recommendation systems and boost customer happiness, user engagement, and revenues. It may also have an effect on how much money is made through cross- and up-selling. The creation, acceptance, and application of suggestions in diverse settings are all included in recommendation behaviour. It is essential to decision-making, user engagement, and the success of companies and online platforms that employ recommendation algorithms to improve user experiences Sharma and Kumar, (2023). Brand trust and brand image have a substantial impact on purchase intention. It is possible to explain 70% of the variation in purchase intention by the relationship between brand trust and image. Additionally, social media marketing is responsible for 45% of variations in brand image and 55% of variations in brand trust (Salhab, H. A. et al, (2023). Because it is the first to apply the perceived costs and benefits of utilising over-the-top (OTT) services to a dual post-adoption model and because it identifies the critical elements influencing the intention to stick with the OTT service. It examines the particular factors that drive customers to stick with the services they already have in the developed OTT industry, and can offer businesses offering OTT services helpful advice for developing efficient platform management plans Hyun Yoon, J. and Ku Kim, H, (2023).

Research Gap

The way in which consumer's judgements of Content quality are influenced by several demographic parameters (age, gender, and cultural background) is frequently overlooked in current studies. Research on how these demographic factors influence the association between

user recommendation behaviour and perceived content quality is needed. Although user engagement is known to be impacted by recommendation algorithms, little is known about how these algorithms interact with perceived content quality to determine user suggestions. Specifically, how does consumers' faith in and use of over-the-top (OTT) platforms change based on how well-recommended material is perceived.

Methodology

Descriptive research was chosen as the study's research design. The purpose of this will be to provide an account of the data and features of the population or phenomenon under study. Under descriptive research, the relationship or association between variables will be shown. A purposive sampling design is adopted for the study. For the study, both primary and secondary data were employed. A questionnaire was created and employed as a tool to gather first-hand information. Secondary data was gathered by means of a thorough examination of books, journals, newspapers, websites, and other materials. The study specifically looks for respondents from these categories who meet predetermined criteria and will be willing to offer the information needed for the study. The respondents were screened to ensure the Content Quality of the OTT Platforms and their Recommendation Behaviour towards the OTT Platforms. The purposive sampling technique was adopted for the study. This method is used to examine a particular subset of the population which is most pertinent to the research issue, this method is especially helpful.

Fig 1. Conceptual Framework

(Source: Yousaf, A. et al.2021)

In the figure 1, the dependent variable in the conceptual framework is recommendation behavior, while independent variables include perceived enjoyment, perceived content quality, and continuous intention to use. The measuring items were created using previously approved instruments and were anchored on a scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The

items for perceived content quality (six items) were adapted from Yousaf, A. *et al.*(2021), Sharma, K. and Lulandala, E. E. (2023), items for perceived enjoyment (eight items) were adopted from Yousaf, A. *et al.* (2021), Holdack, E., et. al (2022), items for continuous intention to use (five items) were adopted from Yousaf, A. *et al.* (2021), (Kuo, C.S. and Hsu, C.C. (2022) and items for recommendation behaviour (four items) were adopted from Yousaf, A. *et al.* (2021), Salhab, H. A. *et al.* (2023).

Research Hypotheses

H1: Perceived content quality positively influences the user’s recommendation behavior.

H2: Perceived enjoyment has a positive effect on user’s recommendation behavior.

H3: Continuous intention to use positively influences the user’s recommendation behavior.

Analysis and Interpretation

Reliability

Table I. Reliability Statistics

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.964	23

(Source: Prepared by Authors, 2024)

The table I shows that the scale with 23 items that makes up the instrument has an elevated state of internal consistency, as indicated by the Cronbach's alpha of 0.964.

Descriptive Statistics

Table II. Descriptive Statistics

S. No	Demography variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Gender	Male	157	51.81
		Female	146	48.19
		Prefer not to say	0	0
		Total	303	100
2	Age	17-22	95	31.35
		23-28	49	16.17
		29-34	24	7.92
		35-40	47	15.51
		41-46	50	16.50
		Above 46	38	12.54
		Total	303	100
3	Employment Status	Employed	160	52.81
		Unemployed	8	2.64

		Student	135	44.55
		Total	303	100
4	Education Level	Higher Education	18	5.94
		Under Graduation	167	55.11
		Post Graduation	109	35.97
		Doctoral or equivalent level	9	2.97
		Total	303	100
5	Marital Status	Married	160	52.81
		Unmarried	143	47.19
		Prefer not to say	0	0
		Total	303	100
6	Monthly Income	Less than Rs.20000	160	52.81
		Rs.20001-40000	143	47.19
		Rs.40001-60000	0	0
		Rs.60001-80000	0	0
		Rs.80001-1,00,000	0	0
		Above Rs.1,00,000	0	0
		Total	303	100

(Source: Prepared by Authors, 2024)

From the table II, there are 303 respondents in the sample, and the distribution of genders is almost equal. Of the respondents, 51.81% are male (157 respondents), and 48.19% are female (146 respondents). Not a single responder selected "Prefer not to say." With 95 responses or 31.35% of the sample, most of the respondents are between the ages of 17 and 22. In the age range of 41–46, 16.50% (50 responders) come next. With only 7.92% of responders being in the 29–34 age range, this is the least represented age group. With representation for every age group from 17 to 46 and beyond, the distribution reveals a wide age range. 52.81% (160 respondents) of the sample are employed, which is a sizable share of the respondents. Students make up 44.55% (135 responses), or a sizable portion of the sample as well. Only 2.64% of respondents (8 people) do not have a job. This suggests that the vast majority of those surveyed are employed or enrolled in school. The respondents' educational backgrounds are diverse, with the majority (55.11%, or 167 respondents) having finished their undergraduate degrees. 35.97% of respondents (109 respondents) have postgraduate qualifications, 5.94% (18 respondents) have finished higher education, and 2.97% (9 respondents) have doctorates or comparable degrees. With 52.81% (160 respondents) of the sample being married and 47.19% (143 respondents) being single, the proportion of married and single respondents is nearly equal. Not disclosing their marital status was a preference shared by all of the respondents. The majority of respondents (52.81%, or 160 respondents) earn less than Rs. 20,000 per month, according to the income distribution. Fourteen other respondents, or 47.19%, make between Rs. 20,001 and Rs. 40,000. The upper income levels (above Rs. 40,001) had no responders. This suggests that those with low to middle incomes make up the majority of the sample.

Regression

Recommendation behaviour (RB) was included as the dependent variable in the regression

model, and perceived enjoyment (PE), perceived content quality (PCQ), and continuous intention to use (CIU) were included as the independent variables. The impact of independent variables on dependent variables was investigated using this method.

Table III. Regression

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.868 ^a	.837	.936	.388	1.709
a. Predictors: (Constant), CIU, PCQ, PE					
b. Dependent Variable: RB					

(Source: Prepared by Authors, 2024)

“R-squared value is used to determine how strongly the independent variables influence the dependent variables. In regression R-squared value was very important because it determines how far the independent variables influence the dependent variables. The adjusted R squared explains how well the model generalizes and it provides cross validation of the model”. From the table III, R-squared value was found to be 0.837, which emphasized 83.7% of variability in the dependent variable was accounted for by all of the independent variables together. Durbin-Watson is used to determine the auto correlation among variables. Field (2009) suggested that the Durbin-Watson value for relatively normal values should range 1.5 to 2.5. In the study value was found to be 1.709 clearly indicating that there was no auto-correlation in the above table.

Table IV. ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	666.758	3	222.253	1474.440	.000 ^b
	Residual	45.070	299	.151		
	Total	711.828	302			
a. Dependent Variable: RB						
b. Predictors: (Constant), CIU, PCQ, PE						

(Source: Prepared by Authors, 2024)

In the table IV, ANOVA was used to determine whether the regression equation, based on the variability in the independent variables Continuous Intention to Use (CIU), Perceived Content Quality (PCQ), and Perceived Enjoyment (PE), could explain a statistically significant portion of the variability in the dependent variable, recommendation behaviour (RB)

Table V. Coefficients

Coefficients ^a	
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Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.094	.250		4.368	.000
	PCQ	.081	.020	.124	4.143	.000
	PE	.181	.014	.380	12.643	.000
	CIU	.363	.016	.538	23.316	.000

a. Dependent Variable: RB

(Source: Prepared by Authors, 2024)

The Table V, Unstandardized and standardized beta coefficients along with their respective t values were provided. The Regression equation derived from the above table is $RB = 1.094 + 0.081(PCQ) + 0.181(PE) + 0.363(CIU)$. Based on the standardized coefficient values, Perceived Content Quality (PCQ), Perceived Enjoyment (PE), and Continuous Intention to Use (CIU) highly influence Recommendation Behaviour (RB).

Correlation

The Pearson correlation coefficients between the four variables—PCQ, PE, CIU, and RB—are shown in Table XI. One indicates a perfect positive correlation (value = 1), a perfect negative correlation (value = -1), and no correlation (value = 0). The ** symbol in this table indicates that all relationships are significant at the 0.01 level.

Table VI. Correlation

Correlations				
	PCQ	PE	CIU	RB
PCQ	1	.860**	.747**	.853**
PE	.860**	1	.750**	.890**
CIU	.747**	.750**	1	.916**
RB	.853**	.890**	.916**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

(Source: Prepared by Authors, 2024)

Based on Table VI, it can be deduced that with a correlation coefficient of 0.860**, a strong positive link relationship is shown. Perceived usability tends to rise along with perceived content quality. With a correlation coefficient of .747**, a strong relationship link is shown. Increased inclination to stick with the service is correlated with higher perceived content quality. With a correlation coefficient of .853**, a strong positive relationship is shown. A higher chance of endorsing the service is closely correlated with better perceived content quality. As said, there is a substantial positive association with a correlation of .860**. With a correlation coefficient of .750**, a strong positive relationship is shown. Higher intention to stick with the service is correlated with easier use. A very strong positive relationship is indicated by the correlation value of .890**. The likelihood of recommending the service is

strongly correlated with its ease of use. The correlation shows a strong positive connection, which is .747**. The correlation shows a strong positive connection, which is .750**. With a correlation coefficient of .916**, there is a very strong positive association. The likelihood of promoting the service is highly correlated with a higher intention to stick with it. A high positive relationship is indicated by the correlation, which is .853**. With a correlation of .890**, there is a very strong positive association. With a correlation of .916**, there is a very strong positive association.

Model Fit Fig. 2. Model Fit

Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

Table VII. Regression Weights

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
RB <--- PCQ	.081	.009	8.563	***	
RB <--- PE	.181	.007	26.273	***	
RB <--- CIU	.363	.010	37.137	***	

(Source: Prepared by Authors, 2024)

The table VII shows the measurement model regression weights, which illustrate the relationships between each construct and its items, are displayed in the above Table XII and it is inferred that Perceived Content Quality (PCQ), Perceived Enjoyment (PE) and Continuous Intention to Use (CIU) have a positive influence on Recommendation Behaviour (RB).

Hypothesis

H1: Perceived Content Quality (PCQ) has a positive influence on Recommendation Behaviour (RB)

H2: Perceived Enjoyment (PE) has a positive influence on Recommendation Behaviour (RB)

H3: Continuous Intention to Use (CIU) has a positive influence on Recommendation Behaviour (RB)

Model Fit Summary

Table VIII. Model Fit Summary

Indices	Value	Suggested value
Chi-square value	7.547	-
DF	4	-
P value	0.104	> 0.05
Chi-square value/DF	1.922	< 5.00
GFI	0.911	> 0.90
AGFI	0.907	> 0.90
NFI	0.934	> 0.90
CFI	0.921	> 0.90
RMR	0.075	< 0.08
RMSEA	0.067	< 0.08

(Source: Prepared by Authors, 2024)

The Table VIII shows the model fit summary. From the above table, it is inferred that the chi-square value of 7.547 with 4 degrees of freedom (DF) yields a P value of 0.104, which is greater than the threshold of 0.05 (Hair et al., 1998). The chi-square value divided by the degrees of freedom (Chi-square value/DF) is 1.922, which is below the suggested value of 5.00 Hair et al., (1998). The GFI (Goodness of Fit Index) value is 0.911, which exceeds the suggested threshold of 0.90 Hu and Bentler, (1999). The AGFI (Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index) value is 0.907, also surpassing the recommended value of 0.90. The NFI (Normed Fit Index) value of 0.934 is above the suggested value of 0.90 Hu and Bentler, (1999). The CFI (Comparative Fit Index) value of 0.921 exceeds the threshold of 0.90 (Daire et al., 2008). The RMR (Root Mean Square Residual) value is 0.075, which is below the maximum acceptable value of 0.08. The RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation) value is 0.067, which is below the recommended upper limit of 0.08 Hair et al., (2006). The model offers a strong fit to the data, as shown by the evaluation of all fit indices (P value, Chi-square value/DF, GFI, AGFI, NFI, CFI, RMR, and RMSEA) which all are at the appropriate levels. Consequently, it appears that the suggested model faithfully represents the observed data.

Findings & Discussion

Descriptive research was chosen as the study's research design. A questionnaire was created and employed as a tool to gather first-hand information. Four constructs make up the research model: Perceived Content Quality (PCQ), Perceived Enjoyment (PE), Continuous Intention to

Use (CIU) and Recommendation Behaviour (RB). Six items make up the construct PCQ Yousaf, A et al., (2021) and Kwon, Y et al., (2021). Eight items make up the construct PE Basuki, R et.al., (2022). Five items make up the construct CIU Kuo, C. S & Hsu, C. C, (2022), Chong, H. X et.al., (2023) and four items make up the construct RB Salhab, H et.al., (2023). The respondents were chosen based on their recommendation behaviour towards the OTT networks and the quality of the content on those platforms. For the study, the purposive sampling approach was used. This approach is particularly useful for looking at a certain subgroup of the population that is most relevant to the research question. Cronbach alpha for the 23 items is 0.964 in reliability statistics, indicating a good degree of internal consistency. With regard to descriptive statistics, the female has a frequency of 146 and the male a frequency of 157. Frequencies for the 17–22 age group are 95, (23–28) 49, (29–34) 24; (35–40) 47; (41–46) 50; and (above 46) 38. Each month, there are 135 students, 8 jobless persons, and 160 employed people. Nine PhD or comparable frequency levels, 167 undergraduate frequencies, 109 postgraduation frequencies, and 18 higher education frequencies are available. There are 160 married people and 143 single people for every 100 people. Income under Rs. 20,000 is 160, and income between Rs. 2000 and Rs. 4000 is 143 per month.

Perceived enjoyment (PE), perceived content quality (PCQ), and continuous intention to use (CIU) were included as the independent variables in a regression model, with recommendation behaviour (RB) serving as the dependent variable. This approach was used to look into how independent variables affected dependent variables. "R-squared value is used to determine how strongly the independent variables influence the dependent variables," Because it indicates the degree to which the independent factors affect the dependent variables, the regression's R-squared value is crucial. The model's cross-validation and explanation of how well it generalises are provided by the modified R squared. The dependent variable's variability was found to be 83.7% explained by all of the independent variables combined, as indicated by the R-squared value of 0.837 in this case. To ascertain the auto correlation between variables, utilise Durbin-Watson. According to Field (2009), the Durbin-Watson value for values that are roughly normal should fall between 1.5 and 2.5. The study's value of 1.709 made it abundantly evident that the above table did not exhibit auto-correlation.

A substantial positive link association is demonstrated, with a correlation coefficient of 0.860**. The perception of content quality tends to increase in tandem with perceived usability. A significant association is demonstrated, with a correlation coefficient of 0.747**. Higher perceived content quality is connected with a greater propensity to remain with the service. An extremely significant positive association is demonstrated, with a correlation coefficient of 0.853**. Better perceived content quality is strongly connected with a higher likelihood of endorsing the service. As previously stated, a strong positive connection ($r = 0.860^{**}$) exists. An extremely significant positive association is demonstrated, with a correlation coefficient of 0.750**. Easier use is associated with a higher intention to continue with the service. The correlation score of 0.890** indicates a very strong positive link. The simplicity of use of the service is favourably connected with the chance of recommending it. The correlation is 0.747**, which indicates a strong positive link. The correlation is 0.750**, which indicates a strong

positive connection. An extremely strong positive link is present, with a correlation coefficient of .916**. A significant positive association exists between the intention to continue with the service and the possibility of promoting it. The correlation, which is .853**, indicates a strong positive association. This indicates a very strong positive link with a correlation of .890**. This indicates a very strong positive link with a correlation of .916**.

It is deduced from the Model Fit Summary that a chi-square value of 7.547 with four degrees of freedom (DF) produces a P value of 0.104, over the 0.05 cutoff (Hair et al., 1998). The value of 1.922 obtained by dividing the chi-square value by the degrees of freedom (Chi-square value/DF) is less than the recommended value of 5.00, as per Hair et al. (1998). The recommended cutoff point of 0.90 is exceeded by the GFI (Goodness of Fit Index) score of 0.911 (Hu and Bentler, 1999). The value of the Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index, or AGFI, is 0.907, which is higher than the suggested value of 0.90 as suggested by Hair et al. (2006). The recommended value of 0.90 is not met by the NFI (Normed Fit Index) value of 0.934 (Hu and Bentler, 1999). According to Daaire et al. (2008), the CFI (Comparative Fit Index) value of 0.921 is higher than the cutoff of 0.90. The value of 0.075 for RMR (Root Mean Square Residual) is less than the 0.08 maximum allowable value (Hair et al., 2006). The Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) value is 0.067, which is less than the 0.08 maximum limit that recommends. The study of all fit indices (P value, Chi-square value/DF, GFI, AGFI, NFI, CFI, RMR, and RMSEA) demonstrates a robust fit of the model to the data and all meet required values. Consequently, it appears that the suggested model faithfully represents the observed data.

Conclusion

The study emphasizes how crucial it is to provide engaging user experiences and high-quality content to maintain user engagement and encourage good word-of-mouth recommendations in the over-the-top (OTT) market. These findings provide insightful advice to OTT platform providers who want to increase user satisfaction and promote continuous usage by implementing focused tactics that put the needs of their users and the quality of their content first.

Implications, Limitations and Future Research

Theoretical Implications

By emphasising particular characteristics that influence user recommendations, this research adds to the body of knowledge on content quality theories already in existence. The study's findings can help improve models of how users interact with digital entertainment environments.

Practical Implications

By concentrating on the qualities that users value most, OTT platforms can use these insights to prioritise the production of high-quality content. More focused and efficient marketing

tactics can be developed by knowing what motivates user referrals. By tailoring information to individual interests, businesses may increase customer happiness and retention.

Limitations

The results of the study may not be as broadly suitable for other demographic groups or geographical areas if the sample size and diversity were insufficient. The study conducted was cross-sectional, it just records a single point in time and does not take into consideration how user preferences or behaviours have changed over time. The conclusions may not apply to all OTT platforms, the data was gathered from one or a small number of them.

Future Research

Deeper insights could be obtained by doing longitudinal research to see how user recommendations are influenced over time by perceived content quality. Subsequent studies could examine several over-the-top (OTT) platforms to determine whether the variables influencing user suggestions differ on each one. It may be beneficial to look into how recommendations are influenced by perceived content quality across various demographic groups (age, gender, and cultural background). Investigating the ways in which user suggestions and judgements of content quality are influenced by developing technologies (e.g., AI-driven recommendations, VR content). Comprehensive qualitative research (such as focus groups and interviews) may offer deeper understandings of the subtleties of user opinions and suggestions. Investigating the relationship between the use of OTT services and traditional media consumption, as well as the effect this has on user recommendations.

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